

UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES AND VETERINARY MEDICINE CLUJ-NAPOCA

the **24th** INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
**LIFE SCIENCES FOR
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT**
25 - 27 September 2025, Cluj-Napoca, Romania

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

No 12/2025

25 - 27 September 2025, Cluj-Napoca, Romania
usamvcluj.ro

TARGETED DELIVERY OF NATURAL ANTIMICROBIALS: ENCAPSULATION STRATEGIES FOR NEXT-GENERATION FEED SUPPLEMENTS

Lavinia Florina CĂLINOIU¹, Dan Cristian VODNAR^{1*}, Adrian-Gheorghe MARTĂU¹,
Chrysanthos STERGIPOULOS², Magdalini KROKIDA², Sofia PAPADAKI³,
Nicoletta TRICHA³, Ioannis MARAMATHAS³ and Apostolos TSOUMANIS³

¹ Faculty of Food Science and Technology, University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary
Medicine of Cluj-Napoca, Romania, ²School of Chemical Engineering, National Technical University
of Athens, 9 Iroon Polytechniou, Zografou 15772, Athens, Greece, ³ Dignity Private Company, 30-32
Leoforos Alexandrou Papagou, Zografou 157 71, Athens, Greece

*Corresponding author, e-mail: dan.vodnar@usamvcluj.ro

Introduction: In the context of sustainable aquaculture and livestock nutrition, bioactive compounds derived from plants and marine resources represent promising alternatives to synthetic additives. However, their instability and volatility limit their direct application. This study, conducted under the Horizon Europe FEEDACTIV project (Grant No. 101086261), aims to overcome these challenges through innovative encapsulation technologies.

Aims: To develop and optimize encapsulation methods for natural bioactives with antimicrobial and antioxidant activity, enabling their integration into functional feed supplements with controlled release properties.

Materials and Methods: Selected bioactive ingredients (olive leaf, lemon peel, Ulva lactuca extracts, and essential oils from eucalyptus, thyme, rosemary, and garlic) were encapsulated using four complementary techniques: spray drying, electrospraying, ionic gelation, and emulsification followed by freeze drying. Natural matrices such as starch, maltodextrin, zein, collagen, alginate, chitosan were evaluated for encapsulation compatibility. Encapsulation efficiency was assessed via HPLC-DAD and GC-MS. Particle size distribution and morphology were characterized using a laser analyzer and SEM. *In vitro* release profiles were measured in phosphate buffer (pH 7.4, 37°C) and modeled kinetically.

Results: All techniques achieved high encapsulation efficiencies, with matrix–bioactive compatibility playing a critical role. Electrospraying and ionic gelation favored controlled, sustained release up to 7 days, while emulsification + freeze drying yielded balanced profiles. SEM images confirmed spherical particle morphology. Select formulations, including Alginate+Oleuropein and Collagen+Eucalyptus oil, demonstrated potential for targeted release in aquafeed applications.

Conclusion: Encapsulation enables the protection and controlled delivery of natural bioactives in feed systems. This work highlights the potential of tailored encapsulant systems to enhance feed functionality and animal health, paving the way for eco-innovative nutrition solutions.

Keywords: aquafeed, bioactive compounds, controlled release, encapsulation, essential oils.

Acknowledgements: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101086261.